

Molecular Basis for Specificity in Protein-Nucleic Acid Interactions[†]

GIRJESH GOVIL

Chemical Physics Group, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Homi Bhabha Road, Bombay-400 005

In most biological processes, the information transfer is controlled by specific protein-nucleic acid interactions. The rules for such interactions are not clearly understood. The specificity of interaction may be in the nature of inter-molecular forces or in the three dimensional structures of the two classes of biopolymers or in both. In this review of the work from our laboratories, an attempt has been made to answer the important question as to how proteins read the language of nucleic acids. The approach is based on theoretical calculations of inter-molecular interaction energies and 2D nmr investigations of the secondary structure of some protein binding sequences of oligonucleotides, such as GGATCC GGATCC (Bam HI recognition sites), GAATTC GAATTC (EcoRI recognition sites) and GAATTC CCGAATTC (repair enzymes binding sites).

PROTEIN-nucleic acid interactions play a crucial role in biological processes^{1,2}. Non-specific binding between these two linear polymers can occur wherever there is a possibility of inter-molecular forces which are strong enough to bind the two molecules together. Such an interaction may then be governed only by the adaptability of proteins and nucleic acids in the sense of stereochemical constraints and may not depend critically on the nature of base or amino acid sequence. One example of non-specific interaction is the binding of histones or polyamines to DNA, a process which plays an important role in the packing and stabilisation of the structure of chromatin. However, from the view of biological control, a more important phenomenon is the selective recognition where by specific base sequences in nucleic acids can be recognised by particular proteins. Such a selective recognition is important in information transfer during replication, transcription, translation, repressor mechanisms and differentiation. Among the important examples of specific recognition of base sequences by proteins are the functional properties of restriction endonucleases, ribosomal proteins, RNA polymerases, repressors *etc.* In many cases, a length of about 3-7 nucleotide units in a long segment of nucleic acid containing 70 to 1000 bases can be selectively recognised by proteins. Thus, in these cases, the binding constant for the specific site differs by a factor of 10^4 to 10^6 from that corresponding to the non-specific sites. Certain proteins have structural rather than base specificity. For example, proteins involved in DNA repair, replication and recombination bind strongly to single stranded regions.

Our knowledge about the molecular events involved in the recognition of nucleic acids by

proteins is rather sketchy. In our laboratories, we have been involved in answering some of the basic questions pertaining to molecular mechanisms in specific protein-nucleic acid interactions. This review is mainly based on our own modest contributions to an explosive and interesting field. A more extensive review has been published recently by Helene and Lancelot³. The question we have asked in this paper is: 'How do proteins recognise specific sequences of nucleotides in long chains of nucleic acid'? The related question as to how 'nucleic acids recognise proteins', is less attractive from biological viewpoint.

Inter-molecular forces in protein-nucleic acid interaction :

The rules for nucleic acid-nucleic acid recognition were enunciated about a quarter of century ago in terms of G : C and A : T(U) base pairing through hydrogen bonding⁴. The complexity of problems in protein-nucleic acid interaction becomes obvious when one realises that here one has to consider a possible combination of at least six different classes of bases (two base pairs G : C and A : T(U) in double stranded systems and four bases for single-stranded systems) with twenty two amino acid residues. In addition, the negatively charged phosphate groups in the nucleic acid backbone and the amide moiety in the peptide backbone provide ideal sites for electrostatic and hydrogen-bonding interactions, respectively.

An understanding of the relative strength of the various types of inter-molecular interactions can be reached through quantum chemical approach. In our laboratories, we have used an approach based on second order perturbation theory⁴ where one expresses the binding energy (E_b) between two

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molecules as a sum of electrostatic (E_e), polarization (E_q), dispersion (E_d) and repulsion (E_r) terms,

$$E_b = E_e + E_p + E_d + E_r \quad (1)$$

The electrostatic interaction is estimated by expressing the molecular charge distribution in terms of multicenter-multipole expansion and then retaining monopole-monopole, monopole-dipole and dipole-dipole terms. The value of E_p is obtained through the use of bond polarisability while E_d and E_r are estimated using Kitaigorodskii potential functions⁵.

As is the case with many other molecular systems, proteins and nucleic acids combine with each other through a set of relatively weak non-bonded interactions. Formation of covalent linkages in recognition processes are rare though not entirely absent. The inter-molecular forces involved include electrostatic, stacking and hydrogen bonding. These interactions may be further stabilised by hydrophobic interactions, metal ions and water bridges. The amino acid residues can thus be classified according to the type of interactions by which they bind to nucleic acids.

Interaction of basic amino acid residues: Positively charged amino acid residues, Lys, Arg and under certain pH conditions His, can interact with the negatively charged phosphate groups in nucleic acid backbone through Coulombic interactions. The binding energies of such interactions are of the same order as that for ionic bonds in inorganic solids^{6,7} (Table 1). The term E_e in equation (1) makes almost 90% contribution to E_b .

Although Coulombic interactions involving point charges are radial in nature, a directional nature to such interactions is imparted by the fact that the charges on the nucleic acid backbone and the protein side chains are highly delocalised. Further, the position and the orientation of the charged groups are governed by the three-dimensional structure of nucleic acids and proteins. It is therefore not surprising that we observe a certain

amount of structural specificity even at the sub-molecular level at which the above calculations have been made. Lys⁺ and His⁺ have a greater affinity for RNA rather than A- or B-DNA. On the other hand, Arg⁺ shows a preferential affinity to A-DNA as compared to RNA. The relative affinities of the three basic amino acid residues follow the order Lys⁺ > His⁺ > Arg⁺. In general, A-DNA forms more stable complexes with basic amino acids than the B-DNA. Conformational variations on the DNA backbone can lead to sites with differential affinity for proteins. Thus, sequence dependent geometrical variations can be recognised by the basic amino acid residues. Secondly, interactions with basic amino acid residue may induce a conformational change in DNA or RNA, thus making it possible for functional groups in proteins to interact at additional sites in nucleic acids.

Arg⁺ can also interact rather strongly with guanine, cytosine and G : C base-pairs of nucleic acids⁸. Here, the proton donor and acceptor groups in the two moieties are involved, leading to two hydrogen bonds. However, the binding energy of 36-39 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 1) is much higher than what one expects on the basis of two hydrogen bonds. In fact, a careful analysis of the various contributions to interaction energies reveal that a large fraction arises from electrostatic interaction between atoms not involved directly in hydrogen bonding. Clearly, such an interaction can selectively recognise G, C regions in double stranded nucleic acids and G and C in single strands.

Interaction with acidic amino acids: A convenient mode of interaction between the two biopolymers can be through hydrogen bonding. Since the hydrogen bonds are directional, such interactions can be highly specific, especially when a particular functional group is involved in two hydrogen bonds. The anionic forms of glutamic acid and aspartic acid can form a pair of hydrogen bonds with guanine in single stranded nucleic acids⁹. There are two interesting aspects of this interaction. First,

TABLE 1—INTER-MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS BETWEEN FUNCTIONAL GROUPS IN PROTEINS AND NUCLEIC ACID

Functional group in protein	Functional group in nucleic acid	Nature of interaction	Binding energy kcal mol	Selectivity of interaction, if any
Arg ⁺ , Lys ⁺ , His ⁺	Backbone (PO ₄)	Electrostatic	90-180	Preference for RNA and A-DNA
Arg ⁺	G, C and G : C	Electrostatic and H bonding	36-39	Highly selective to G and C in both single and double stranded regions
Glu ⁻ , Asp ⁻	G	Electrostatic and H bonding	23-25	Selective to G in single stranded regions
Trp, Tyr, Phe, His	Bases and base-pairs	Stacking	6-18	Preference to single stranded regions or kinked structure. G, C rich regions are preferred
Asp, Glu, Asn, Gln	Bases and base-pairs	Hydrogen bonding	6-15	Greater binding energy for G, C rich region
Peptide back bone	Bases and base-pairs	Hydrogen bonding	1-10	Highly dependent on the long range adaptability of protein structure—preference for double stranded regions
Hydrophobic amino acids	Hydrophobic regions	Van der Waal and hydrophobic	< 3	Non selective

the interaction energies (23-25 kcal mol⁻¹) are a factor of two higher than that expected from purely hydrogen bonding considerations. Again, a large contribution to the binding energy in these cases comes from electrostatic interactions involving atoms not directly involved in hydrogen bonding interactions. Secondly, since the interaction for these residues is limited to G in single stranded-nucleic acids, the recognition process can be highly selective.

Hydrogen bonding with neutral amino acid residues : A number of bonding schemes involving two or more hydrogen bonds between Asp, Glu, Asn and Gln on one hand and G, C, T, A and U on the other, are theoretically possible⁸. The binding energies for these complexes vary between 6-15 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 1) and follow the following order,

where, X=Glu, Asp, Gln or Asn. The bases generally prefer binding with Gln and Asn. Thus, single stranded nucleic acid can bind to protein sequences containing above residues in a variety of ways.

A more interesting aspect is the possibility of the binding of above amino acid residues with double helical nucleic acids. With A : U or A : T base pairs, hydrogen bonding with Asn, Gln, Asp and Glu can occur only in the major groove of B-DNA. With G : C base pairs, interaction can occur both in the major groove and in the minor groove but complexes in the major groove are more stable by almost 3-4 kcal mol⁻¹. Glu and Asp have a higher affinity for G : C base pairs while Gln and Asn can bind to G : C and A : U(T) base pairs with equal ease.

A large contribution (almost 90%) to the total binding energies in these cases arises from electrostatic term.

Aromatic amino acids : Aromatic amino acid residues Tap, Tyr, Phe and His can bind to nucleic acid bases and base-pairs through stacking interactions⁹⁻¹¹. The predominant contribution to the total binding energy for these complexes comes from the dispersion term. Due to a favourable contribution from hydrophobic effects, stacking can assume an even greater importance in aqueous solutions. Energy minimisation show that a vertical separation of 3.2 to 3.4 Å between the aromatic residues of proteins and bases of nucleic acids leads to the most stable configuration. Such an interaction will lead to a partial ordering of single stranded nucleic acids such that the bases on adjoining nucleotide overlap with the aromatic amino acids on either side leading to an inter-nucleotide separation of 6-7 Å. However, in the case of double stranded nucleic acids in A, B or Z form, the base-pairs are already stacked with vertical separation of 2.8-3.4 Å and the intercalation of aromatic amino acids is sterically prohibited. The nucleic acid may, there-

fore, have to unfold locally to allow the amino acid residue to get in. A more interesting possibility is that the protein binding regions have kink structures¹² where the inter-nucleotide distances are ideally suited for an aromatic residue to interleave between adjoining base-pairs. An analysis of the geometrical pattern of base-aromatic amino acid interaction shows that the heteroatom of the bases overlap with the aromatic part of the amino acids. Further, the aromatic moieties of the two components overlap only partially supporting the selective book mark hypothesis^{13,14} which states that the nucleotide sequences can be recognised by amino acid chain acting like book-marks.

In general, it is found that G among the purines and C among the pyrimidines, have higher binding energies. Thus, in actual protein-nucleic acid interactions G, C rich regions will be preferred both in single and double stranded nucleic acids.

Hydrogen bonding involving peptide backbone : An interesting mode of interaction of proteins with nucleic acids is the involvement of the amide-NH and C=O groups in the peptide backbone with nucleic acid bases and base-pairs¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Such an interaction is not critically dependent on the amino acid sequence and can occur in bridge-region of two other amino acids involved in interaction through one of the mechanisms described above. The major groove in double stranded nucleic acids is preferred for such interaction.

Other interactions : In addition to the interaction schemes listed above, the protein nucleic acid interactions can be stabilised by van der Waal and hydrophobic interactions. These interactions are weak and non-directional. Hence, they are not likely to be important in specific recognition though they may make an additional contribution to a scheme otherwise stabilised by stronger inter-molecular forces. Metal bridges, e.g. PO₄⁻...Mg²⁺...Asp⁻ are possible and these can make substantial contribution to binding energy. However, it is not clear how such interactions on their own can lead to specificity. Finally, formation of covalent linkage between peptide and nucleotide fragments can lead to the formation of nucleoproteins. Again, such interactions are not involved in recognition processes.

Role of secondary structure of nucleic acids :

While the mechanisms described in the previous section lead to a certain degree of specificity both in terms of sequence and structure, it is not clear whether the protein binding regions of nucleic acids are structured in a way so as to achieve a highly specific binding or whether such a shape is induced by the protein so as to reach optimum interaction by the functional group.

The structure of nucleic acid has attracted renewed interest in recent years following the results of potential energy calculations, nmr and X-ray crystallography on small molecules which indicated considerable conformational flexibility^{2,18}.

Our group has made substantial contribution in delineating conformational preferences of polynucleotides¹⁹⁻²³. These results indicate that the proposed structure of B-DNA may be an oversimplification for the conformation of natural DNAs. In fact, by careful control of experimental conditions, at least three different forms have been characterised for polynucleotides. These are A, B and Z. Other imaginative models have been proposed but at the moment there are no experimental proofs to support them. The characteristic of these structures are as follows.

(i) B-DNA forms a helix of 10.5 base-pairs per turn of 34 Å height and has a diameter of 20 Å. The corresponding numbers are 12, 44.6 Å and 18 Å for Z-DNA and 11, 25 Å and 25 Å for A-DNA.

(ii) The repeating unit is mononucleotide for A- and B-DNA and the base conformation is *anti*. The important difference in the two structure is that deoxyribose ring has a C3' *endo* geometry in the former and C2' *endo* geometry in the latter. In Z-DNA the repeating unit is a dinucleotide with bases in the alternating *syn* and *anti* conformation and generally, the sugar geometry alternates between C2' *endo* and C3' *endo*.

Under physiological condition, all evidences point to B-DNA as the most dominant structure¹⁸. However, there can be local conditions or steric constraints which may cause localised variations in the structure. Such microheterogeneities in the structure may then become hot points for recognition. We have recently worked out solution conformations of a number of protein-binding sequences which support such a hypothesis. The technique used for this purpose is the recently developed 2D FT nmr. The main advantage of nmr is that it can provide structural information in solutions⁴ unlike the conventional technique of X-ray crystallography which is applicable to solid state. The two dimensional *J*-correlated spectra (COSY²⁴, COSS²⁵, SUPERCOSY²⁶ etc.) provide information on the *J* couplings which in fact can be correlated with dihedral angles along the various chemical bonds⁶. The NOESY spectra provide information on all the short interproton distances (<5 Å) in the molecule. These two pieces of information can be combined with chemical shifts to detect conformational heterogeneity in structure of nucleic acids.

Structure of GGATCC GGATCC : This sequence has two binding sites for Bam HI endonuclease. The unit recognised by this enzyme is GGATCC. In a double helical system, the nucleic acid segment is cleaved as indicated by arrows,

Using 2D nmr, we find^{27,28} that at ambient temperature, the overall conformation is a right-handed B-DNA with most of the deoxyribose units acquiring a conformation close to C2' *endo*. However, the sugars attached to G1 and G7 adopt a C3' *endo* conformation leading to C2' *endo*-C3' *endo* junctions. Such structure have been seen earlier in complexes of short segments of DNA with drugs, and have been named as kinks¹². The kink structure has the unique feature that the base-pairs are separated by more than 6 Å making it feasible for Bam HI to detect and interact at these site through an aromatic amino acid.

GAATTCGAATTC : This dodecamer has two specific recognition sites for ECOR I restriction endonuclease indicated by arrows,

The unit recognised is GAATTC. Also, the T-C-G segment is significant since the enzyme DNAase-I is known to cut DNA preferentially at TCG sites. Our studies²⁹ on this double helical system shows that while the molecule attains a right-handed structure it is different from either A or B DNA since the sugar acquire a O1' *endo* conformation. Moreover, the cytosine at position 6 in the sequence slips away from T5 and acquire a backbone conformation which is different from the rest of the molecule.

GAATCCCGAATTC : This molecule³⁰ has the same sequence as the previous one except that there are two additional cytosine residues, C7 and C8 which do not have

complementary guanines. Such mismatches are significant for recognition by repair enzymes, synthetase and polymerase. We observe that the geometry of the oligonucleotide differs significantly in the mismatch region with C6, C7 looping out on either side.

CGCGCGCGCGCG : This oligonucleotide is interesting since at high salt concentration the molecule undergoes a transition from B to Z form³¹. Such transitions have been well characterised in CG-series and are brought about by high concentration of cations. It is possible that the cationic interaction at the phosphate sites induces a C3' *endo*-C2' *endo* sugar pucker variation in the backbone. One of the questions we hope to answer is whether such a transition are to be brought about locally by specific binding with basic amino acids Lys⁺ or Arg⁺.

The examples discussed above are indicative that the molecular conformation of DNA may play a vital role in specific recognition.

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References

1. C. HELENE and G. LANCLOT, *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.*, 1982, **39**, 168.
2. G. GOVIL and R. V. HOSUR, "Conformation of Biological Molecules", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1982.
3. J. D. WATSON and F. H. O. CRICK, *Nature (London)*, 1953, **171**, 787.
4. P. OLAVARIE in "Intermolecular Interactions; From Diatomics to Biopolymers", ed. B. PULLMAN, Wiley, New York, 1978.
5. J. CAILLET and P. OLAVARIE, *Acta Crystallogr., A*, 1975, **31**, 448.
6. N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL, *Biopolymers*, 1984, **23**, 1979.
7. G. GOVIL, N. V. KUMAR, M. RAVI KUMAR, R. V. HOSUR, K. B. ROY and H. T. MILES, *J. Biosci.*, 1985, **52**, 645.
8. N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL, *Biopolymers*, 1984, **23**, 1995.
9. N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL in "Conformation in Biology", eds. R. SRINIVASAN and R. H. SARMA, Adenine Press, 1982.
10. N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL, *Biopolymers*, 1984, **23**, 2009.
11. N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL in "Molecular Basis of Cancer", ed. R. REIN, Alan R. Liss, New York, 1985.
12. H. M. SOBELL in "Biological Macromolecules and Assemblies", eds. F. A. JURNAK and A. MCPHERSON, Wiley, 1985, Vol. 2.
13. P. E. BROWN, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1970, **213**, 282.
14. E. J. GABBAY, K. SANFORD and C. S. BAXTER, *Biochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 3429.
15. R. V. HOSUR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1980, **49**, 928.
16. R. V. HOSUR, N. V. KUMAR and G. GOVIL, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 23.
17. R. V. HOSUR and A. POHORILLE, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 33.
18. W. SAENGER, "Principles of Nucleic Acid Structure", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1984.
19. G. GOVIL and A. SARAN, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1971, **30**, 621.
20. G. GOVIL and A. SARAN, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1971, **33**, 899.
21. A. SARAN and G. GOVIL, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1971, **33**, 407.
22. R. TEWARI, R. K. NANDA and G. GOVIL, *Biopolymers*, 1974, **13**, 2015.
23. G. GOVIL, *Biopolymers*, 1976, **15**, 2903.
24. W. P. AUE, E. BERTHOLDI and R. R. ERNST, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1982, **64**, 2229.
25. R. V. HOSUR, M. RAVI KUMAR and A. SHETH, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1985, in the press.
26. R. V. HOSUR, K. V. R. CHARY, A. KUMAR and G. GOVIL, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1985, **62**, 123.
27. R. V. HOSUR, M. RAVI KUMAR, K. B. ROY, TAN ZU-KUN, H. T. MILES and G. GOVIL in "Magnetic Resonance in Biology and Medicine", eds. G. GOVIL, O. L. KHETRAPAL and A. SARAN, Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 1985.
28. M. RAVI KUMAR, R. V. HOSUR, K. B. ROY, H. T. MILES and G. GOVIL, *Biochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 7708.
29. K. V. R. CHARY, R. V. HOSUR, G. GOVIL, TAN ZU-KUN and H. T. MILES, communicated.
30. R. V. HOSUR, M. RAVI KUMAR, K. V. R. CHARY, A. SHETH, G. GOVIL and H. T. MILES, unpublished.
31. A. SHETH, M. RAVI KUMAR, R. V. HOSUR, G. GOVIL and H. T. MILES, unpublished.